

Paper Review: Zero-Shot Recommendation as Language Modeling

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In this paper review, we replicate the results of *Zero-Shot Recommendation as Language Modeling* to evaluate the reproducibility of its findings. We provide a detailed outline of our results and highlight the challenges that we faced in the reproduction process. We also compare the results obtained in the initial paper with a more recent version of the GPT model to evaluate improvements in the recommendation viability of the more advanced language model architecture.

CCS Concepts: • **Computing methodologies** → **Natural language processing**; • **Information systems** → **Recommender systems**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Zero-shot learning, reproduction, language model

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1 Introduction

In the course of the course *Experiment Design for Data Science* we were tasked to reproduce the paper *Zero-Shot Recommendation as Language Modeling* [3], which compares the Language Model (LM)-based recommendation approach with a standard matrix factorization algorithm.

The paper proposes an alternative model for movie recommendation based on the standard LM trained on the unstructured text corpora, which is a very different approach to the usual collaborative filtering and content-based methods that require structured training data, which is often hard to obtain in large quantity and good quality.

The paper concludes that LMs trained on unstructured text corpora are a viable option for movie recommendations that in certain cases outperform matrix factorization algorithms, specifically Bayesian personalized ranking (BPR). We want to review these results and update them by using the newer LM models GPT3.5 turbo and GPT4o-mini.

2 Experiment Setup

2.1 Paper Summary

To reproduce the results in *Zero-Shot Recommendation as Language Modeling* the experiments are based on the public MovieLens 1M dataset [1], which contains user-item ratings. Ratings are categorized as positive (≥ 4.0) or negative (≤ 2.5), and users with at least 21 positive and 4 negative ratings are selected, which produces 2,716 users. 20% of the users are reserved for testing, with 1 positive and 4 negative ratings reserved for evaluation. Movie titles are simplified by removing the year and reordering the articles.

The primary evaluation metric is Mean Average Precision at Rank 1 (MAP@1), which measures the accuracy of top-ranked recommendations. Pretrained GPT2 models of 2 different sizes (base and medium) are used to compute relevance scores based on the likelihood of prompts constructed from user preferences. Baseline comparisons include

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Bayesian Personalized Ranking (BPR) and BERT-based Next Sentence Prediction (NSP). Prompt designs are derived from analyzing Reddit comments to identify common patterns in how users list similar movies.

Upon e-mail request, first author Damien Sileo remarked that the boundaries to select users is arbitrary but that increasing it would otherwise reduce the number of valid users and increase memory usage.

2.2 Paper Reproduction

The Python code for the original paper is publicly available and accessible via Google Colab¹. Since the paper’s original release in 2022, the Python packages used in the code had been updated, so we have overwritten the default package imports with the latest versions based on the paper’s release date. The original data pre-processing used hardcoded numeric bounds and incorrectly treated the actual minimum and maximum as the infimum and supremum. We corrected this inconsistency and used parameterized thresholds, but the change had no effect since the original bounds were already fine-tuned to the data. Otherwise, now flaws were obvious, though the code be optimized in running time through parallelization, (i.e. instead of `for i in tqdm(users)`), though this may not affect the running time (ca. 30min) remarkably. The evaluation metrics were logged in a *Weights&Biases* ("Wandb") dashboard and exported to create figures and conduct statistical tests within this report.

2.2.1 Bayesian Personalized Ranking (BPR). In the original paper, Sileo et al. also utilized a BPR model. Specifically, the implementation offered in *Cornac*², an comparative framework for multimodal recommender systems, which is based on a paper by Rendle et al [2]. As the code for this part of the original experiment was unavailable, we aimed to reproduce the experiment ourselves using Cornac’s BPR implementation. We used the parameters (i.e. learning rate) and kept to the data pre-processing as reported in the paper.

3 Results

3.1 Prompt Structures

First, we compared all 6 prompt structures with various number of movies mentioned in the prompts (0,1,2,3,5,10,15,20). The LM model for this experiment is GPT2 base. Figure 1 demonstrates our results. In the original paper, the prompt type $\langle m_1, \dots, m_n \rangle, \langle m_i \rangle$ led to the best performance. In our case, the prompt *Movies similar to* $\langle m_1, \dots, m_n \rangle$ was the best. However, the difference in performance also varies depending on the run, the subset of test users and number of movies used in the prompt, so small variations can be expected. In another run only using 5 movies in the prompts (the choice of $n=5$ is motivated by results in Figure 2), we achieved a similar ranking of prompts. The MAP@1 values for all prompts are in line with those presented in the paper.

3.2 Number of Movies in Prompts

In Figure 2 we showcase the results of our attempt to reproduce Fig. 2 from the original report for the MAP@1 depending on the number of movies per user sampled in the input prompt. Since the exact LM is not specified, we created multiple runs of GPT2-base model and one with GPT2-medium to check the consistency of the results. We used the prompt $\langle m_1, \dots, m_n \rangle, \langle m_i \rangle$, since it was the most successful one in the original paper, and was most likely used for the plot. We were not able to reproduce the confidence bounds from the original plot because the standard deviation for the precision measurements was normally as high or even higher than the precision value itself, so the bounds would be

¹Original paper’s Python Code, Google Colab

²Cornac framework GitHub page

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Fig. 1. MAP@1 using different prompt structures with GPT2-base model. [M] is a comma-separated list of movies.

too wide to read the plot. It was confirmed, across multiple runs, that the number of movies in prompt that leads to the best precision is $n = 5$ for the GPT2-base model. However, GPT2-medium model shows a clear preference for the $n = 10$. The MAP@1 scores are also in line with those in the paper.

Fig. 2. MAP@1 for different runs of GPT2-base and GPT2-medium LM depending on the number of movies sampled in the prompts.

Upon the same e-mail request, Damien Sileo further remarked that the x-axis in Fig. 2 was rendered linearly even though it was not. As reported, the peak should be around $x=5$ which aligns with our findings.

3.3 Comparison of Models

In Figure 3 we compare performance of the LMs GPT2 base and GPT2 medium, matrix factorization algorithm BPR and two version of BERT model (base and large).

3.4 Statistical Significance in Differences

Since the authors did not provide the logs for their experiments with GPT2 models, we could not perform statistical tests between their implementation with ours. We performed a one-way ANOVA on our implementation.

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Fig. 3. MAP@1 comparison between GPT2, BERT and BPR.

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The statistical analysis revealed a significant difference in precision scores among the evaluated models. The one-way ANOVA test yielded a highly significant result ($F = 25.48$, $p < 0.0001$), indicating that at least one model performed differently from the others. Post hoc analysis using Tukey's HSD test showed that both GPT2 models (base and medium) significantly outperformed the BERT models (base and large) in precision ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, GPT2 medium achieved a significantly higher precision than GPT2 base ($p = 0.0143$), identifying it as the best-performing model. In contrast, the two BERT models showed no significant difference ($p = 0.9986$), indicating comparable performance. These results suggest that GPT2 models, particularly GPT2 medium, are more effective for this recommendation task than BERT-based models.

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4 Comparisons With More Recent LLMs

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After reproducing the experiments, we also wanted to test out how more recent LLMs behave in a similar experimental setup. We selected a GPT3.5-turbo and a GPT4o model for our tests. Both models can be accessed via a REST API from OpenAPI³.

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Unfortunately, this API does not support a method for directly retrieving log probabilities for a given set of output token (this approach was used in the experiment). Therefore we adjusted the prompt for those two models a bit and utilized the `client.chat.completions` api for delivering the the prompt. First, we primed the LLM by providing the following prompt input:

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Prompt:
"Given a list of favorite movies and a list of suggested movies, rank the suggested movies by probability of
likeability based on themes, genres, and storytelling style. Provide only a concise, easily parsable ranked list in
the output format: 1 > 2 > 3 > 4 > 5 (most to least likely).
Favorite Movies: Fargo, The Departed, Breaking Bad
Suggested Movies: 1=Sin City, 2=Beetlejuice, 3=Winnetou, 4=Sicario, 5=Game of Thrones"
Example Output:
4 > 1 > 5 > 2 > 3
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For each user we create the prompt with favorite and suggested movies and parsed the ranking from the response. To ensure compatibility with the existing evaluation logic, we converted the parsed ranking into log probabilities. Since

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³<https://platform.openai.com>

the absolute values were irrelevant for our purposes, we focused only on preserving the ranking order (so we assigned values of negative ranking order -1, -2 and so forth). such that the movie at position 1 got the highest probability value. From this result we could calculate the MAP@1 like in the original experiment. Aside from the updated prompt and the use of different LLMs, the test setup remained consistent with the previous experiment.

For generating our results we let the logic run for a total of 2000 users (executed in blocks of 200 users each).

Fig. 4. Optimal number of movies sampled in prompt: comparison of GPT models.

Fig. 5. Results of the additional experiment. GPT4o and GPT3.5-turbo outperformed the GPT2 models.

As seen in Figure 4, for our new prompt and GPT models, the optimal number of movies is either 1 for GPT3.5 or 15 for GPT4o-mini. For all models we observe a different number of optimal number of movies in the prompts. Overall, our prompt, combined with the more advanced LLMs, outperformed the GPT2 models, as seen in Figure 5 by achieving over 60% MAP@1 for the current state-of-the-art GPT4o-mini.

However, BPR is still better than GPT3.5-turbo when provided with bigger training data, and its performance is improving with the increase in size of the training data. It even nearly matched the performance of the newest GPT4o-mini model, but did not surpass it because we did not have enough training data available. It suggests that BPR might still perform better than the newest LMs but we could not confirm this. Nevertheless, the results show that LLMs may be a valid approach to tackle the cold-start problem.

5 Conclusion

We were able to confirm that the pre-trained language models perform well in the movie recommendation settings, with more advanced and newer models becoming even stronger at this task. While advanced LM models performed even better or the same as BPR (at its largest training set), we notice the upward trend in the performance of matrix factorization algorithm still with increasing amount of data. However, the rapid development in the domain of generative AI presents a good reason to replicate the results of this paper in the future.

We learned that reproducibility issues can arise early, such as from missing dependency versioning. Reproducing the original experiment highlighted the value of reproducibility papers: they allow non-authors to independently verify insights and reported results. We also found that providing contact information independent of academic institutions (e.g., ORCID ID) can make it easier to reach out.

6 Acknowledgements

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